

2-Chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Determination of Iron

(MRS.) V. A. JADHAV

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 17 August 1993, accepted 3 November 1993

A large number of spectrophotometric reagents have been reported for determination of iron(III)¹. 2-Chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (2-chloro-QAT) was found to be most suitable reagent for determination of iron(II). Iron forms complex with (2-chloro-QAT). Moreover, some elements like Bi^{III} and V^V interfere seriously in his method. The present communication reports more sensitive and selective method for spectrophotometric determination of iron, in which Fe^{II} forms a complex with (2-chloro-QAT).

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of iron(II)-2-chloro-QAT complex containing 1.7905×10^{-4} M of iron(II) and 1.02×10^{-3} M reagent at pH 6 using reagent blank was recorded in 400–520 nm region. The suitable wavelength for the determination of iron was found to be 418 nm. Molar absorptivity of the complex was found to be 0.3463×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The colour development was instantaneous and absorbance remained constant for 45 min. A 1.5 ml of 1.02×10^{-3} M reagent and a pH of 6 were found optimum.

The yellow complex of iron-(2-chloro-QAT) followed Beer's law upto 5 ppm of iron(II). Sandell sensitivity² was $0.016 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Fe^{II} at 418 nm for $\log I_0/I = 0.001$. The optimum range is 3–8 ppm of Fe^{II}.

Molar composition of the complex studied by Job's and mole-ratio methods, was found to be 1 : 2 with respect to metal and reagent.

Sn^{II} interfered seriously by tin(II) whereas Ni, Ce, Cu, Bi^{III}, V and HPO₄²⁻ interfered strongly. Zn, Co, Ni, Mn, Ca, Cd^{II}, Pd^{II}, Os^{VIII}, Th^{IV}, Ti^{IV} and fluoride did not interfere.

The method was tested by satisfactory analysis of sample of iron upto 200 μg in aliquot. The method is selective for iron in the presence of fluoride, acetate, EDTA, W^{VI} and U^{VI}. The method is simple, sensitive and rapid, and may be used for analysis of Fe in industrial samples.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spekol spectrophotometer and a Philips PR 9405L pH meter with glass-calomel combination electrode (Philips PV 9014) were used.

A stock solution of Fe^{II} (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving ammonium ferrous sulphate hexahydrate (A.R.) in distilled water containing concentrated H₂SO₄ (2–3 drops) and standardised³. (2-Chloro-QAT) (0.027 g) was dissolved in DMF-water (1 : 1) and diluted to 100 ml. A 20% (w/v) solution of ascorbic acid was prepared and used for reduction of Fe^{III}.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution (containing upto 10 ppm Fe and 1.02×10^{-3} M reagent solution (1.5 ml), was added 2% ascorbic acid (1 ml) to prevent atmospheric oxidation of iron followed by addition of the buffer solution (pH 6, sodium acetate-acetic acid), and then diluted to 10 ml with DMF-water (3 : 3) and the absorbance was measured against blank.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to express her thanks to Head, Chemistry Department, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, for facilities.

References

- 1 G. H. AYRES and A. K. ROCH, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962,

26, 332 S. M. KHOPKAR and A. K. DE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1960, **22**, 223; S. G. KAWATKAR and C. K. BHASKARE, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 189; B. A. ABBASI, B. G. BHAT and R. S. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 215

2. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Trace Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959. p. 83.
3. A. E. VOGEL, " A Text Book of Quantitative, Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longman, London, p. 293.